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Research Article

**THE DIAGNOSTIC ROLE OF FNAC WITH THE
HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CORRELATION OF SALIVARY
GLAND SWELLINGS****¹Dr Nimra Mir, ²Dr Saira Naseer, ³Dr Hafiz Muhammad Shafique ur Rehman****¹Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore., ²Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore., ³Multan
Medical & Dental College****Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** To assess the role of fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) of salivary gland swellings with histopathological correlation.**Study design:** prospective study.**Methodology:** One hundred and forty patients were prospectively examined from September 2019 to September 2020 in the Surgical Unit-II of Sir Gangaram Hospital, Lahore. All these swellings were subjected to FNAC using 10cc syringes out of 22 no. needle and histomorphology were assessed.**Results:** Among 140 patients, 80% of them were non-cancerous, including 61% benign and 31% malignant, and 20% non-cancerous. The most common benign neoplasm was multiforme adenoma, and the most common malignant lesion was mucocutaneous carcinoma. The maximum number of cases among non-neoplastic individuals was related to chronic salivary gland inflammation. In our study, FNAC has a sensitivity of 94.54% and a specificity of 80.95% for neoplastic lesions.**Conclusions:** FNAC proved to be a useful diagnostic tool in the assessment of salivary gland swelling due to its simplicity, painless technique, excellent patient compliance, rapid diagnosis and cost effectiveness.**Key words:** FNAC, pleomorphic adenoma, muco-epidermoid carcinoma, salivary gland swellings**Corresponding author:****Dr. Nimra Mir,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Swelling of the salivary glands is often a diagnostic challenge with regard to its site of origin, neoplastic (benign or malignant) and non-neoplastic lesions. Most of them occur in the parotid gland, and a small percentage in the submandibular, sublingual and smaller glands. Salivary gland injuries account for 2-6.5% of all head and neck cancers in adults. Parotid salivary gland tumors account for 3% of all head and neck tumors and 0.6% of all tumors in the human body. Salivary gland swellings are usually available with thin aspiration cytology (FNAC) and are not biopsied due to the risk of developing a fistula or tumor implantation in the case of cancer. There is no evidence that such complications occur with FNAC. The role of FNAC in the diagnosis of salivary gland swelling is well documented, therefore traditional open biopsy is no longer justified due to the risk of tumor spread and damage to the facial nerve. FNAC has been observed to be highly sensitive to distinguish neoplastic salivary gland lesions from non-neoplastic ones.

The FNAC has supporters and opponents as it is a diagnostic procedure that surpasses a combination of physical examination and radiological evaluation. It can also be done in children over the age of seven.⁸ However, various retrospective studies have found that preoperative FNAC has little clinical impact as many parotid tumors ultimately require surgery. This study was undertaken to evaluate and analyze salivary gland swelling using the FNAC method and to correlate cytological findings with histopathology. Cytology allows for a clear distinction between

salivary and non-salivary lesions, neoplastic and non-neoplastic swelling, and gives decisive directions for therapeutic treatment.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

One hundred and forty patients were prospectively examined from September 2019 to September 2020 in the Surgical Unit-II of Sir Gangaram Hospital, Lahore. Detailed clinical history, results Each case was recorded local, general and system research. All 140 patients underwent FNAC with a 10-cc syringe and 22 no. needles and their results compared with the histopathological diagnosis obtained from the surgical specimen.

RESULTS:

The 140 patients included 84 women and 56 men, most aged 21 to 40 years (70 cases, 50%). The most affected gland was the parotid gland, which occurs in 57.2% of cases. There were 112 neoplastic lesions and 28 non-neoplastic lesions (Table 1).

Of the 112 neoplastic lesions, 68 were benign and 44 were malignant. The most common benign neoplasm was multiforme adenoma, and the most common malignant neoplasm was muco-epidermal carcinoma (Table 2).

In 20 cases, neoplastic lesions were diagnosed on the basis of FNAC and specific typing could not be performed. In the non-neoplastic group, there were 20 cases of neoplastic lesion, 4 cases of tuberculosis and 6 cases of cystic disease. However, the following correlation is observed between FNAC cytology and the histopathological diagnosis of our study (Table 3).

Table 1: *FNAC of salivary gland swellings*

Non Neoplastic	Neoplastic		Neoplastic Lesions no specific diagnosis
	Benign	Malignant	
Chronic Sialadenitis 18	Pleomorphic Adenoma	56	Mucoepidermoid Carcinoma 16
Cystic Lesions 6	Warthins tumour	2	Adenoid cystic carcinoma 14
Tuberculosis 4			Squamous cell carcinoma 4
Total 28		58	34 20

Table 2: Histopathological diagnosis of salivary gland swellings

Non Neoplastic		Neoplastic			
		Benign	Malignant		
Chronic Sialadenitis	20	Pleomorphic Adenoma	62	Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	22
Necrotizing Sialometaplasia	2	Warthins tumour	4	Adenoid cystic carcinoma	16
Cyst Sialometaplasia	2	Benign Lympho-epithelial lesion	2	Squamous cell carcinoma	4
Tuberculosis	4			Adenocarcinoma	2
Total	28		68		44

Table 3: Correlation observed between the FNAC cytology & Histopathological diagnosis of salivary gland swellings

Salivary gland Lesions	FNAC cytology	Histopathology
Pleomorphic Adenoma	56	62
Warthins tumour	02	04
Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	16	22
Adenoid cystic carcinoma	14	16
Squamous cell carcinoma	04	04
Neoplastic lesions with no specific diagnosis	20	00
Adenocarcinoma	00	02
Chronic Sialadenitis	18	20
Cystic lesions	06	02
Tuberculosis	04	04
Benign Lymphoepithelial lesion	00	02
Necrotizing Sialometaplasia	00	02
Total	140	140

DISCUSSION:

The FNAC technique is widely used as a diagnostic tool in the treatment of various head and neck injuries. In the opinion of many staff members, FNAC is considered an accurate and safe method of diagnosis, while others have argued that due to its false-positive and false-negative results, it has little role in the clinical treatment of patients.¹⁰ However, preoperative cytology helps to distinguish between benign and malignant salivary gland lesions, which helps in each case to plan the extent of the operation. In our study, there is a slight advantage of women, ie

84 women and 56 men. The parotid gland was involved in the majority of 57.2% of cases.

In other retrospective studies, the parotid gland was involved in 69 (81%) cases. There were 58 (41%) benign neoplasms, and in previous studies, the incidence of benign neoplasms was 40-61%. Ten percent of our cases are malignant as retrospective data showed 6% -13% of other authors. Twenty percent of the cases were non-cancerous, while some previous studies have seen up to 40% of the non-cancerous lesions.

Of the 62 cases diagnosed as multiforme adenoma by histopathology, 56 were correctly identified by FNAC. In the remaining 6 cases, 2 were diagnosed as neoplastic, 2 as adenocystic carcinoma and 2 as cystic lesions. In retrospective studies, 50% of multiforme adenomas were observed.

The most common malignant tumor was mucocutaneous carcinoma in 22 cases. In 14 cases diagnosed as neoplastic lesions on FNAC, mucocutaneous carcinoma was found in histopathological examination, a similar correlation was observed in previous studies.

Preoperative diagnosis of malignant lesions allows the surgeon and the patient to better discuss and plan further management, and mild diagnosis saves the patient several days of anxiety related to the diagnosis of surgical biopsy.

In fourteen cases of adenocystic carcinoma diagnosed histologically on the basis of FNAC, the diagnosis of the neoplastic lesion was confirmed and a 96% correlation was demonstrated. In the histopathological examination, two cases of adenocarcinoma were diagnosed as neoplastic. When it comes to salivary gland tumors, many consist of different proportions of epithelial, myoepithelial and stromal cells. These functions are responsible for the diagnostic limitations of FNAC.

In the case of Warthin's tumor, a 90% correlation was found in the histopathological examination. In our series, we diagnosed two cases of Warthins' tumor on FNAC, but histopathological examination found it to be chronic inflammation of the sail knot. In our study of chronic sagitis, we observed that the cytohistological correlation was 90%, compared to about 81.8% in the previous study. In four cases of tuberculosis, we found the correct diagnosis on FNAC, showing a 100% correlation. Our study is characterized by a sensitivity of 94.4% and a specificity of 80-95% for neoplastic changes.

CONCLUSIONS:

FNAC is a reliable technique for the pre-operative diagnosis of salivary gland tumors. Correct cytological diagnosis allows you to avoid unjustified surgery. The minimally invasive nature of FNAC provides valuable information for further planning. However, there are still a few cases that may not be properly diagnosed by cytology, in which case histopathology is the best method of obtaining a final diagnosis.

Therefore, FNAC has been found to be a simple, non-invasive, cost-effective and rapid diagnostic tool for

salivary gland swelling to assist in the surgical treatment of these patients.

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